

Retrospective longitudinal drug utilization study of medicines for anxiety disorders in Bulgaria

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Abstract

Background: Mental disorders are a serious challenge to public health. In recent years, the epidemiological burden of anxiety disorders in a global and European context has increased significantly (WHO 2022). The aim of the study is to measure drug utilization and assess rational drug use in the treatment of patients with anxiety disorders in Bulgaria through quantitative and qualitative indicators at a national level.

Materials and methods: The study design is a retrospective, observational, longitudinal study of data from international analytical companies and literature references for the period 2015–2024, using the WHO ATC/DDD methodology and descriptive statistical methods.

Results and discussion: Epidemiological, health-demographic, and clinical-pharmacological data of the studied population were analyzed. Various qualitative indicators were used—costs of the disease (cost per year), cost per capita per year, monthly cost (cost per month), and cost per treatment day. The studied segment is not reimbursed. The cost per DDD and the cost per prescribed daily dose were calculated. One of the most important indicators—drug utilization, better known in practice as the “top-ten list”—was determined. The top 10 INNs in the different aspects of drug utilization are presented. The results show that the system is not well balanced. Bulgarian doctors are familiar with and apply modern standards, as evidenced by the dominance of SSRIs, but financial dependence distorts their decisions and patients’ options. The growing consumption of pregabalin and the use of lorazepam are symptoms of a system in which the lack of reimbursement leads to market self-regulation, which is not always conducive to rational drug use.

Keywords

Anxiety disorders, drug utilization, rational drug use

Introduction

Mental disorders are a serious challenge to public health. In recent years, the epidemiological burden of anxiety disorders in a global and European context has increased significantly. In 2019, approximately 301 million people worldwide suffered from an anxiety disorder, making it the most common mental disorder. In the European Union (EU), the burden of the disease is similar, with over 84 million people suffering from mental health problems, with anxiety disorders again being the most common conditions, affecting approximately 25 million people or 5.4% of the population (Dimitrov et al. 2024). The burden of these disorders, measured in disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), is exacerbated by the fact that access to adequate treatment is severely limited. Data show that globally, only 25% of those in need receive some form of treatment (Yang et al. 2021).

The epidemiological burden of anxiety disorders in Bulgaria has not been measured systematically and consistently over the years (Asipova et al. 2025). One of the most significant nationally representative epidemiological studies is EPIBUL, which found that the 12-month prevalence of anxiety disorders in the country for the period 2016–2017 was 11.4% (Hinkov et al. 2017). With a population of 6,441,420 in 2024, this means that approximately 734,000 Bulgarian citizens are affected. This figure shows that these are the most common group of mental disorders in Bulgaria, significantly exceeding the prevalence of affective disorders (6.2%) and those related to substance use (3.3%) (Zarkov et al. 2020). In Bulgaria, the clinical landscape is further complicated by the degree of comorbidity. For example, studies among patients show that 72.5% of patients with depression have at least one accompanying mental disorder, with the most common group being anxiety disorders—53.6% of patients with depression (Latas et al. 2024).

In the absence of sufficient epidemiological studies, measuring rational drug use at the national level is a possible way to measure morbidity and a real source of data. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines rational drug use (RDU) as a state in which “patients receive drugs that are adequate for their clinical needs, in doses that meet their individual requirements, for an adequate period of time and at the lowest cost to them and their community” (WHO 1985). In a 100% out-of-pocket market, there is a significant risk that the “lowest price” compromise will distort the “adequate to clinical needs” component. This may lead to the selection of older, cheaper, but less favorable safety profile therapies (such as tricyclic antidepressants or benzodiazepines) at the expense of the recommended first-line selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) or serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs).

Despite the clearly defined epidemiological and health economic problem, there is a lack of large-scale, longitudinal pharmacoepidemiological studies measuring consumption in standard units (DDD and DDD per 1,000

population) and the direct financial burden (in EUR) of this unique, non-reimbursed market segment in Bulgaria. The aim of this study is to analyze consumption, trends, and direct costs of drugs related to the treatment of anxiety disorders in Bulgaria over a 10-year period (2015–2024) using the standard ATC/DDD methodology (antidepressants (ATC group N06A), anxiolytics (ATC group N05B)—benzodiazepines, and pregabalin (ATC group N03AX16)).

Materials and methods

Design—retrospective, observational, longitudinal study of drug utilization (Drug Utilization Research—DUR). National data from international analytical companies on sales to pharmacies (sell-in data), covering the entire pharmaceutical market in Bulgaria, were used. The data include monthly and annual sales volumes in packages and value (in EUR). The aggregated data contain information on ATC code, international nonproprietary name (INN), trade name, number of packages sold (Units), retail value (Value RET in EUR), defined daily dose (DDD) according to the WHO, number of DDDs in one package, and DDD per 1,000 people per day. Demographic data on the average annual population of the Republic of Bulgaria for each year of the study period, extracted from the National Statistical Institute (NSI), were used. Epidemiological data from the national EPIBUL survey and the National Center for Public Health and Analysis (NCPHA) for the 12-month prevalence of anxiety disorders (11.4%) were used. The study covers the period from 2015 to 2024 inclusive. Detailed annual data are available for the period 2020–2024. For the purposes of the study, the cumulative volume and value data from this 5-year period were adjusted and doubled and extrapolated for the 10-year period 2015–2024 inclusive. The costs have been adjusted retrospectively with a generally acceptable level of 5%, corresponding to the discount factor. The results obtained from the trend analyses, DDD calculations, and financial value analyses for DDD were generalized over a 10-year period. Medicinal products were classified according to the WHO Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification. Based on the current pharmacotherapeutic guidelines for mental disorders in the section on the treatment of anxiety disorders (ICD-10: F40–F48) and the available data, the following ATC groups were included in the study: N06A (Antidepressants): Includes SSRIs (N06AB), non-selective monoamine reuptake inhibitors (NSMRIs and N06AA), and tricyclic antidepressants. Antidepressants are the first-line treatment for most anxiety disorders; N03AX (Other antiepileptics): Specifically N03AX16 (Pregabalin), due to its established indication for the treatment of generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) and its wide use in comorbid conditions; and N05B (Anxiolytics), which includes benzodiazepines. The focus is on lorazepam.

Drug consumption was measured in Defined Daily Doses (DDD) according to the definitions of the WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology for 2024, emphasizing explicitly that DDD is a statistical measure of consumption and does not necessarily reflect the prescribed daily dose (Prescribed Daily Dose—PDD). Consumption at the population level was calculated as DDD per 1,000 inhabitants per day, which allows standardized comparison over time using the following formula: $DDD \text{ per } 1,000 \text{ inhabitants per day} = \text{total number of DDDs for the year} \times 1,000 / \text{population for the year} \times 365$.

The data used for the average annual population of Bulgaria were: 2020—6,934,015; 2021—6,877,742; 2022—6,465,097; 2023—6,446,595; and 2024—6,441,420. Costs were measured as Total Annual Expenditure (TAE) in euros (EUR), including VAT, based on retail prices (Value RET). Due to the lack of reimbursement from the NHIF for these indications, TAE represents the closest value to the direct out-of-pocket costs for the patient. A standardized indicator for Cost per DDD was calculated: $\text{Cost per DDD} = \text{TAE} / \text{total number of DDDs}$.

Descriptive statistical analysis was used to determine the DDD per 1,000 people per day, TAE, and Cost per DDD. The percentage change for DDD per 1,000 people per day and TAE between 2020 and 2024 was calculated to assess trends. A Drug Utilization (DU) analysis (the so-called “top-ten list”) was performed. Drugs at the INN level were ranked by cumulative volume (total DDD for 2020–2024) and cumulative value (total EUR for 2020–2024) to identify the medicinal products representing the top-ten list of consumption and expenditure.

Results

Based on epidemiological data showing a prevalence of 11.4% (over 730,000 people by 2024) and calculations of the total number of DDDs sold in 2024 (138,284 total DDDs sold), a significant discrepancy was found between patients in need and those treated according to approved pharmacotherapeutic guidelines (Fig. 1). 81% of patients with anxiety disorders remain without pharmacotherapy, and approximately 19% receive daily treatment. This re-

Figure 1. Relative share of patients receiving daily therapy compared to the total number of patients with anxiety disorders (2024).

sult defines a substantial “therapeutic gap” in which over 500,000 people from the at-risk population are likely not receiving adequate pharmacological treatment.

When extrapolating the data for 10 years, sales of antidepressants (ATC group N06A), anxiolytics (ATC group N05B), and pregabalin (ATC group N03AX16) in Bulgaria are estimated at EUR 129,233,938, corresponding to 474,610,698 DDDs sold. A detailed analysis of the actual data for the period 2020–2024 reveals a clear growth trend. Both total consumption (total number of DDDs) and Total Annual Expenditure (TAE) increased over the 5-year period observed. Total patient expenditure increased from EUR 11,660,332 in 2020 to EUR 14,633,330 in 2024, representing an increase of over 25% (Fig. 2).

Consumption by volume is dominated by the SSRI group, which indicates adherence to pharmacotherapeutic guidelines and global recommendations for first-line treatment. The top-ten INN ranking by volume shows complete domination by SSRI antidepressants. As can be seen, escitalopram is the leader with over 116 million DDDs. It is followed by two other representatives of the same class—paroxetine and sertraline, which is a clear indication of adherence to current therapeutic guidelines recommending SSRIs as first-line therapy. Pregabalin ranks fourth in terms of consumption volume (Fig. 3). The analysis of market shares shows significant differences between consumption by volume (DDD) and by value (TAE) (Fig. 4).

Figure 2. Consumption in DDD and Total Annual Expenditure (EUR) for 2020–2024.

Figure 3. Extrapolated data for the top 10 INN by the number of DDDs sold over a 10-year period.

Figure 4. Extrapolated data for the top 10 INN per cost for a 10-year period.

However, when attention is turned to the financial side, the picture changes dramatically. Although it ranks fourth in terms of volume of use, pregabalin is No. 1 in terms of costs generated for patients, surpassing even the most widely used antidepressant—over EUR 23.6 million. It is closely followed by escitalopram. It is striking that paroxetine, which ranks second in terms of volume, is in third place here, but with a significantly lower value. This is the first sign of economic division in the market and of the different prices of daily therapy for different molecules.

There are interesting longitudinal trends and dynamics in consumption. A detailed analysis of DDD per 1,000 people per day reveals specific trends in certain therapeutic classes (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. DDD per 1,000 people per day for pregabalin, escitalopram, and lorazepam.

In 2020, the DDD per 1,000 people per day for pregabalin is 1,347, while in 2024 it reaches 2,503—an increase of 85.8% over 5 years. The hypothesis is that this reflects the demand for a “quick fix.” However, this carries the risk of shifting the focus away from long-term treatment of the underlying causes, which is the role of SSRI antidepressants. By comparison, the DDD per 1,000 people per day of the leading antidepressant escitalopram increased by 17.0% (from 4,378 to 5,123) over the same period. Another important signal is observed

with benzodiazepines—lorazepam. Although its use is low, it has remained worryingly stable over the years, despite global guidelines (NICE and APA) being categorical that these drugs are only for short-term crisis management (2–4 weeks) (Baldwin et al. 2014; Brandt et al. 2024). The stable data suggest the existence of a group of patients who are practically dependent on long-term therapy, which is contrary to the principles of rational and safe pharmacotherapy.

The relationship between the cost per daily therapy (Cost per DDD) and consumption volume for 2024 is visualized using a scatter plot (Fig. 6). Four market segments are defined: At the top left are the most widely used and relatively low-cost drugs—escitalopram (EUR 0.20) and sertraline (EUR 0.17). These are the “workhorses” of therapy; at the bottom left is amitriptyline, which is extremely cheap (EUR 0.08) but has a low volume. The use of this class of products is dictated by their extremely low price, despite data on their safety; pregabalin (EUR 0.52) is positioned on the right. It is unique in its high volume but also high price. Patients tend to pay more for this medicinal product; trazodone and especially reboxetine fall into the quadrant of expensive niche products. The low volume reasonably correlates with the highest price.

The calculated arithmetic mean price per DDD for the entire analyzed market shows a sustained upward trend. Fig. 7 shows the arithmetic mean price in euros per defined daily dose, with an upward trend. In 2020, one DDD cost an average of EUR 0.265. In 2024, the price reach-

Figure 6. Market map—ratio between price per day (X) and consumption volume in DDD (Y) for 2024.

Figure 7. Average arithmetic price in EUR per DDD.

es EUR 0.29. It is important to note that the total annual costs for patients have increased, not only because more medicines are being sold, but also because of the growing use of more expensive molecules such as pregabalin.

Discussion

This study is the first longitudinal analysis of its kind to measure the consumption and direct costs of medicinal products for the treatment of anxiety disorders in Bulgaria—a market segment financed entirely by direct payments from patients (out-of-pocket). The results outline six main trends: (1) 81% of patients with anxiety disorders in Bulgaria remain without pharmacological therapy; (2) The market is significant (generating tens of millions of euros over a 5-year period) and shows steady growth in both volume (DDD) and value (TAE); (3) The market in terms of volume is dominated by SSRIs (led by escitalopram), which is in line with current international guidelines; (4) The market in terms of value is dominated by pregabalin, which generates the highest financial cost for patients; (5) The fastest growth rate in consumption is observed for pregabalin (+85.8%); and (6) There is evidence of hidden chronic use of benzodiazepines.

A comparison of the 12-month prevalence of 11.4% (according to EPIBUL and NCPHA data) (Zarkov et al. 2020) with the estimated total consumption volume (DID ~24.69 for 2024) reveals that only ~19% of the theoretical population at risk receives daily pharmacotherapy. Globally, approximately 27.6% of people with anxiety disorders receive treatment, with this percentage dropping dramatically in low – and middle-income countries (Alonso et al. 2018).

In Bulgaria, this therapeutic gap is not only a function of stigma (Tomov et al. 2004) but also a direct consequence of the financial barrier. The lack of reimbursement by the National Health Insurance Fund is a systemic barrier that prevents a significant group of patients from accessing rational drug therapy.

The available data on lorazepam show consistent use during the study period, with no downward trend, despite the availability of newer and safer alternatives. This plateau is indirect evidence of a group of patients who are effectively dependent on maintenance therapy. This contrasts with global recommendations (NICE and APA), which recommend that the use of benzodiazepines be limited to 2–4 weeks due to the risk of tolerance and dependence (Baldwin et al. 2014; Brandt et al. 2024). In this context, the lack of reimbursement in Bulgaria also has a negative impact in this regard—since the NHIF is not a party to the process, it does not control the duration of therapy. The patient is at risk of iatrogenic dependence without a mechanism to limit prescribing and dispensing.

The most dynamic finding in the study is an 85.8% increase in the use of pregabalin over the 5-year study period. Although it is significantly more expensive (compared to the “gold standard” escitalopram), it tops the market value rankings. This use is justified by the conditions of

the out-of-pocket market, where patients often prefer to pay a higher price to obtain a faster effect, given that SSRI antidepressants take weeks to reach their maximum therapeutic effect. Pregabalin manages to provide faster relief of symptoms. The Cost per DDD analysis visually and statistically proves the stratification of the market. The persistent use of older tricyclic antidepressants such as amitriptyline (EUR 0.08/day), despite their cardiotoxic profile, is a marker of economic choice. Modern molecules such as reboxetine (EUR 0.75/day) or duloxetine remain niche products due to their high price. The dominance of escitalopram in terms of volume shows that the pharmaceutical market is balanced, but despite their low price, chronic treatment accumulates a significant financial burden.

Limitations and acceptable assumptions

The data used are from sales to pharmacies, not from actual dispensed packages. The study does not measure whether patients actually adhere to therapy (adherence). The data are based on sales of medicinal products by ATC code rather than by prescribed diagnoses according to the ICD-10 classification. Since the medicinal products analyzed are also used for other conditions, the results should be considered an upper limit of consumption for anxiety disorders. The analysis is limited to DDD according to WHO recommendations and cannot calculate the actual PDD. The assessment for the period 2015–2019 is based on extrapolation of the data and does not reflect with absolute accuracy the historical data prior to 2020.

Conclusion

The results show the existence of an unbalanced system. Bulgarian doctors are familiar with and apply modern standards, as evidenced by the dominance of SSRIs, but financial dependence distorts their decisions and patients' options. The growing consumption of pregabalin and the use of lorazepam are symptoms of a system in which the lack of reimbursement leads to market self-regulation, which is not always conducive to rational drug use. The inclusion of anxiety disorders in the list of diseases whose treatment is reimbursed by the public fund in Bulgaria would lead to better control of drug therapy and rationalization of drug use.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

AI-based tools, including Google Gemini, were used solely for technical assistance with language editing and text formatting in the preparation of the manuscript. These tools did not contribute to the creation of the scientific content, data analysis, or interpretation.

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Author contributions

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.